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Compensated LGAD — an innovative design of thin silicon sensors for very high fluences

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ABSTRACT. This contribution presents a new development of radiation-resistant silicon sensors based on Low Gain Avalanche Diode (LGAD) technology, combined with 30 μm -thick substrate, intrinsically less affected by radiation. The key feature of LGAD technology is its internal gain, which generates large and fast signals, suitable to track temporally charged particles with excellent time precision (~ 30 ps). An innovative design of the multiplication layer has been developed and fabricated, exploiting the compensation of acceptor and donor dopants, to recreate the effective acceptor gain implant of standard LGAD technology. The proof of concept of compensated LGADs was produced by Fondazione Bruno Kessler, at the end of 2022. In this contribution, more relevant characterization measurements on first irradiated prototypes of compensated LGADs, in the presence of external stimulus by particle beam for signal generation, will be presented and discussed. The compensated LGAD technology has the ultimate goal to operate in radiation environments where the irradiation fluence will exceed 10^{17} $n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$, maintaining the time-tracking capability of standard LGAD sensors.

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KEYWORDS: Radiation-hard detectors; Radiation damage to detector materials (solid state); Solid state detectors; Timing detectors

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1 Introduction

Future high-energy and high-intensity hadron colliders for high-energy physics will require precise particle space-time tracking in harsh radiation environments, where the expected irradiation in the innermost layers of tracking detectors will range from 10^{17} to $10^{18} n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$ [1]. The need to design future tracker detectors able to operate in harsh conditions is leading to the development of new radiation-hard 4D-tracking sensors with excellent space- and time-tracking performance. The recent developments of the thin Low-Gain Avalanche Diodes (LGADs) technology [2], have made them suitable candidates to instrument 4D-trackers in future high energy physics experiments. The main figure of merit of LGADs is the internal avalanche multiplication mechanism (gain mechanism), which enables charged particles timing with a resolution of 30 ps up to an irradiation fluence of $2.5 \cdot 10^{15} n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$ [3]. To enhance their resistance to radiation, an innovative design of LGADs, so-called compensated LGAD, has been developed and manufactured [4, 5]. In a standard LGAD the multiplication layer is obtained by implanting a thin layer of acceptors ($p^+ \sim 10^{16}\text{--}10^{17} \text{ atoms}/\text{cm}^3$) underneath the n^{++} electrode; this design manifests the total deactivation of implanted acceptor atoms already at a fluence of $10^{16} n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$, as shown in figure 1. In the compensated LGADs, the multiplication layer is obtained through the overlap of a p^+ and an n^+ implants: the difference between the concentration of acceptor and donor dopants forms an effective concentration, similar

Figure 1. Gain implant acceptor profile from LGAD sensors unirradiated (black) and irradiated with neutrons (green) at fluence of $1 \cdot 10^{16} n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$. Both profiles were extracted from Capacitance-Voltage measurements (method described in [7], chapter 4).

to standard LGADs. The compensated design is more resistant to radiation, since both acceptor and donor implants undergo deactivation with irradiation (Acceptor/Donor removal law $\propto e^{-c_{A/D}\Phi}$, where from preliminary studies $c_D \sim 2c_A$ [6]), if properly engineered, their difference will remain constant preserving the multiplication layer.

2 Proof of concept of compensated LGADs

The first prototypes of compensated LGADs were produced by Fondazione Bruno Kessler in 2022, in the EXFLU1 batch [8]. The compensated LGADs have been produced on 6-inch wafers, with an epitaxial substrate of active thickness 30 μm . Boron (B) and Phosphorus (P) have been used as acceptor and donor dopants, respectively.

Three different combinations of $B-P$ have been chosen to investigate the compensation mechanism: 2 – 1, 3 – 2 and 5 – 4. For the first two combinations, three different doses of boron (a , b and c) have been implanted, to optimize the compensation (table 1). Moreover, the multiplication region of Wafer 13 has been enriched with Carbon (C) atoms, to mitigate the effect of acceptor removal, when an acceptor implant is exposed to irradiation. All the B , P and C doses listed in table 1 are in arbitrary units and refer to the FBK reference dose (dose = 1) implanted in standard LGADs.

Table 1. Split table of compensated LGAD wafers. The dose coding reported in the table is $a < b < c$, $2c < 3a$ and $3c < 5a$. Doses 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 are expressed in arbitrary units.

Wafer	B dose [a.u.]	P dose [a.u.]	C dose [a.u.]
6	2a	1	-
7	2b	1	-
8	2b	1	-
9	2c	1	-
10	3a	2	-
11	3b	2	-
12	3b	2	-
13	3b	2	1
14	3c	2	-
15	5a	4	-

The doses of B and P reported in 1 come from process simulations (Simulations performed with Silvaco Technology CAD tool [9]), in order to properly engineer both implants. As example of this simulation process, the doping concentration of a compensated gain implant 5 – 4 is shown in 2-left. The real implanted profiles have been extracted through Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS) [10], in order to understand unexpected electrical behaviour of the devices [5]. SIMS showed lower and shallower B implant, and larger P implant (2-right) compared to simulated ones, respectively.

An irradiation campaign with neutrons on compensated LGADs was done at the JSI TRIGA reactor [11], up to a fluence of $5 \cdot 10^{15} n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$. The electrical characterisation of irradiated compensated LGADs revealed a promising response in terms of the wafer 13 gain [5]. These results stressed the necessity for more investigation on irradiated samples.

Figure 2. Left: simulated implant profiles in 5 – 4 compensated LGADs, using TCAD Silvaco [9]. The dashed light and dark blue lines correspond to Boron and Phosphorus concentrations, while the red line represents the total effective doping obtained from their difference. Right: doping profiles extracted through Second Ion Mass Spectroscopy (SIMS) technique, from a 5 – 4 compensated LGAD. The color code corresponds to the one in the left picture. Adapted from [5]. CC BY 4.0.

3 Beam test on irradiated compensated LGAD

A single pad from Wafer 13 (3B–2P+1C), with an active surface of 1.7 mm^2 and irradiated with neutrons at $2.5 \cdot 10^{15} n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$ has been tested during a beam test. The beam test was conducted at the DESY beam test facility (Hamburg), using a 4 GeV/c momentum electron beam [12]. The experimental setup consisted of the Device Under Test (DUT) placed, along the beam line, between a trigger and a time reference sensor. The trigger sensor was a single pad standard LGAD of surface 10 mm^2 , while the time reference a Photonis MCP-PMT [13] with a timing resolution of 5 ps. The readout chain of the DUT consisted of two amplification stages, a UCSC board followed by a Cividec Broadband Amplifier of amplification factor 20 dB; the signals from the DUT were acquired by a WaveRunner 8208HD Teledyne Lecroy oscilloscope with a sampling rate of 10 GSample/s and a bandwidth of 2 GHz.

Figure 3 shows the shape of a single signal acquired with the described readout chain. The time duration of the signal ($\sim 1 \text{ ns}$) and its rise time ($\sim 400 \text{ ps}$) are consistent with values observed on $30 \mu\text{m}$ -thick standard LGADs. These signal features indicate that a compensated gain implant do not affect the known mechanism of signal formation in an LGAD sensor and that compensated LGADs can achieve the same timing performance as standard ones. Figure 4-left shows the evolution of

Figure 3. Example of signal readout from the sensor biased at 310 V and at a temperature of -40°C .

the gain with the applied reverse bias, the curve has an exponential trend, typical of LGAD sensors. The DUT has gain values between 2 and 12, corresponding to 0.6 and 3.6 fC, in a range of bias 250–340 V. The gain is estimated as the collected charge divided by 0.3 fC, corresponding to the amount of charge generated by a Minimum Ionizing Particle in 30 μm of silicon. The results of the time resolution analysis are reported in figure 4-right.

The time resolution decreases from 46 ps to 39 ps, followed by a slight increase for bias above 325 V. This worsening of the time resolution can be explained by the increase of the noise with the bias, from 1.5 mV to ~ 2.7 mV passing from 325 V to 340 V of bias.

Figure 4. Gain (left), time resolution and RMS noise (right) of the wafer 13 (3B-2P+1C) and the fluence of $2.5 \cdot 10^{15} n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$ as a function of the applied reverse bias. The measurements were performed in a range of temperature between -35°C and -50°C .

4 Conclusion

The proof of concept batch of p^+n^+ compensated LGAD sensors was produced and released by FBK in 2022. Different strategies of Boron and Phosphorous concentration have been implemented, namely 2 – 1, 3 – 2 with one carbonated wafer (W13), and 5 – 4. Boron and Phosphorous implants obtained from the production process differ from what was predicted by the process simulation. Compensated LGADs have been irradiated with neutrons up to $5 \cdot 10^{15} n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$. In particular, W13 sensors irradiated to $2.5 \cdot 10^{15} n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$ has been characterized during a beam test in DESY. A timing resolution of 39 ps has been reached at a moderate gain of 6.9. These results indicate the capability of compensated LGAD sensors to reach performance in terms of gain and time resolution comparable with standard LGADs.

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